

Neighbor-informed burnup correction for gadolinium depletion with APOLLO3[®]

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ABSTRACT

The computation of PWRs with gadolinium-loaded pins presents a challenge in two-step deterministic calculation schemes, especially when the 3D core calculation uses a cell-homogenized spatial mesh. Indeed, the influence of rim effect, captured by the lattice calculation but partially lost through homogenization, makes the estimation of the local burnup values in the gadolinium-loaded cells difficult. This impacts heavily the quality of the interpolation of homogenized nuclear data in those cells. In this work, we study a correction proposed in the literature, called the Neighbor-Informed Burnup Correction. It consists in replacing the temporal parameter with which the nuclear data for gadolinium-loaded pins are interpolated, with a new parameter that the code is able to estimate more accurately. The method is evaluated on the PRATIC benchmark with the APOLLO3[®] deterministic code, from a 2D assembly to a full 3D core. Performances of NIBC are compared to the standard method, and show a reduction of the error during the gadolinium depletion.

Keywords: PWR, deterministic, gadolinium, depletion

1. INTRODUCTION

Gadolinium is a common burnable neutron absorber used in several thermal nuclear reactors. Indeed, some of the gadolinium isotopes have large thermal absorption cross sections. Their presence at the beginning of the cycle enables an offset of the initial high reactivity caused by the presence of fresh fuel, reactivity that cannot be completely handled through boron shim or control rods insertion. Gadolinium is then depleted during the cycle, thus compensating for the loss of reactivity due to the irradiation of the fuel. Use of gadolinium allows for flattening the power distribution between fresh fuel assemblies and depleted ones. This enables an optimization of the core loading that leads to longer cycles, for example by increasing the enrichment in fissile isotopes in the fuel assemblies.

In most PWRs, gadolinium is dispersed in the UO_2 matrix as Gd_2O_3 . This combination of burnable absorber and fuel is then used as in regular fuel pins, although the U^{235} enrichment in the gadolinium-loaded fuel pins (referred to as gadolinium pins) is usually lower for thermal conductivity purposes.

When computing nuclear cores using neutronics deterministic codes, gadolinium presents some challenges for the calculation schemes, such as added spatial heterogeneity in the assemblies, resonances that require an additional energy self-shielding treatment, and a specific isotopic depletion behavior. In particular, in standard two-step calculation schemes that rely on a cell-homogenized core calculation rather than a coarser homogenization, the depletion behavior of gadolinium isotopes becomes difficult to predict accurately. In [1], the authors propose a quite innovative yet simple method to circumvent this challenge, called the Neighbor-Informed Burnup Correction (NIBC). They show a clear improvement on the gadolinium depletion accuracy on 2D core calculations.

In this work, we implement and apply the NIBC on a series of cases, from a 2D assembly to a 3D core. These cases are based on the PRATIC benchmark [2], and the depletion calculations are performed with the APOLLO3[®] deterministic code [3] through the SIGAR framework [4].

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2. GADOLINIUM DEPLETION AND NIBC

2.1. Issues with Gadolinium Depletion in two-step Calculations

Under irradiation, fuel pellets containing gadolinium exhibit a strong rim effect. This is due to a high spatial self-shielding effect of gadolinium. As a result, the capture rates on the periphery are higher than in the center of the pellet and thus the concentrations of gadolinium isotopes display a strong radial gradient.

In most two-step calculations, the so-called lattice calculation produces the homogenized nuclear data for the core models using a precise representation of the cells geometry inside of a Cartesian lattice. In particular, to take into account the aforementioned rim effect, gadolinium pins are usually refined into a certain number of concentric rings (more than for standard fuel pins, in which the rim effect is less severe). This enables to have several fine flux calculation and depletion regions, and thus reduces the approximation induced by the meshing.

In core calculations, this rim effect cannot be taken into account in conventional two-steps codes, which at most can handle cell-homogenized geometries. Thus the effect can only be taken into account through the data homogenized by the lattice part. However, as explained later in this section, the effect is replicated only partially in the core calculation, due to the loss of information during the homogenization.

2.2. Core Depletion Calculations

2.2.1. Microscopic and macroscopic depletions

There are two methods to treat depletion of isotopes in core calculations.

The first one, named the macroscopic depletion, does not call any actual depletion solver and relies solely on interpolating the macroscopic cross sections of the concerned isotope in the homogenized nuclear data. This interpolation is usually based on the local burnup of each depleting region. However, the lattice depletion is only partially representative of the core depletion and, for isotopes such as xenon, macroscopic depletion is not suitable due to their relatively fast build-up or disappearance dynamics.

The other one is the microscopic depletion, for which the isotope is explicitly treated with a depletion solver, obtaining isotopic concentrations that can be quite different from the homogenized nuclear data, leaving only the microscopic cross sections of the isotope to be interpolated. This enables taking into account the more realistic 3D reaction rates to compute the concentrations, at the cost of additional numerical operations. In theory, this method is the most precise if the quality of the cross sections interpolation is ensured, which is usually not the case for gadolinium as explained later in the section.

In most calculation schemes, a combination of those two methods is used, microscopic for isotopes that require a fine tracking along the cycle, and macroscopic for the remaining ones.

2.2.2. Nuclear data interpolation along burnup

When interpolating nuclear data along the burnup parameter, one of the challenges is the estimation of the local burnup value for each cell contributing to the global burnup. For a depletion numerical scheme in which the flux is considered as constant in each time interval, the local burnup value at step $i + 1$ is determined using the reaction rates at i , so that this burnup value is strongly dependant on the fineness of the depletion steps.

As explained in [1], for regions in which the energy is essentially coming from fission, an error on the burnup value tends to be compensated on the following steps, since overestimating the energy at a step yields less fissile material at the end of the step, thus making less fissile material for the calculation of the burnup on the next step. Therefore, what we can call a "negative feedback" takes place.

On the other hand, for pins with a lot of absorbers such as gadolinium, overestimating the energy at a step yields less absorber isotopes at the end of the step, thus less material to absorb neutrons at the next step. Here a positive feedback takes place and an error on the burnup value is accumulated during the depletion in those pins, until the gadolinium is completely depleted. Hence in the case of gadolinium depletion, whether microscopic or macroscopic, the value of the local burnup used for interpolating nuclear data is flawed. The idea behind the NIBC is to circumvent this by changing the interpolation parameter to one that the code is able to better estimate.

The main cause for all of these issues is the coarseness of the depletion mesh, which cannot be refined too much because of the computational burden. Indeed, in 3D core cycle calculation for instance, neutronics is solved at each depletion step and at least coupled with thermal-hydraulics feedbacks.

2.3. The Neighbor-Informed Burnup Correction

Introduced in [1], the NIBC aims at replacing, for the gadolinium pins, the local temporal parameter used for interpolating homogenized nuclear data. Instead of using the standard one, which is the local burnup, the NIBC suggests relying on the local burnups of the cells around the gadolinium one which, in standard PWR assemblies, are composed of fuel or guide tube cells. Hence, a simple calculation of the mean value of the immediate neighbor's burnups is done for each global burnup, and this value is used to replace the local burnup as interpolation parameter in the gadolinium cells.

3. APPLICATION OF THE NIBC

3.1. Benchmark Description

The PRATIC benchmark [2], a heavily gadolinium-loaded boron-less SMR core, is selected for testing the performances of the NIBC. As shown in Figure 1, each one of its assemblies contain gadolinium pins, with a gadolinium content of 8 wt.% with a fuel enrichment in ^{235}U of 2.5 wt.%. The other fuel pins are enriched in ^{235}U at 5.0 wt.% for the external assembly, 3.5 wt.% for the internal assembly and 2.5 wt.% for the central assembly. The startup core layout is shown in Figure 2. Detailed specifications are available in [2].

Figure 1. Schematic view of rod type distribution in external (a), internal (b) and central (c) assembly types of the PRATIC benchmark ([2])

Figure 2. Schematic view of the PRATIC startup core layout ([2])

In order to have a suite of increasingly complex simulations, three cases have been selected: the two-dimension internal assembly, the 2D core (as a radial cut in the active part) and finally the full 3D core.

All these cases are studied under nominal conditions. Thermal-hydraulics, critical boron, xenon equilibrium and rod insertions are not considered here.

3.2. Description of the Calculation Scheme

The neutronics calculation scheme used for the study of NIBC relies on a standard two-step method. It is based on the deterministic code APOLLO3[®] [3], developed at CEA, and is setup with SIGAR [4], which is an APOLLO3[®]-based framework dedicated to the modelling of PWRs. In particular, the core calculation uses the MINOS diffusion solver with 2 energy groups, with a cell-homogenized spatial mesh. A SuperHomogénéisation (SPH) equivalence with a Flux-Volume normalization is performed on the homogenized cross sections. The depletion is done on all isotopes microscopically, except for gadolinium isotopes that are treated macroscopically. Indeed, one of the conclusions of [1] is that the microscopic calculation of gadolinium isotopes entails larger errors than for macroscopic calculation, which we also observe in our computations.

3.3. NIBC Implementation

The implementation of the NIBC is quite straightforward. The goal is to interpolate the macroscopic cross sections for the gadolinium cells not with their own burnup values but with the mean value of the neighboring cells' burnups. From a standard two-step calculation scheme with APOLLO3[®], three additional operations have been implemented thanks to APOLLO3[®]'s Python API:

- in the input cross sections library that automatically uses the pin-homogenized burnup as the temporal axis to interpolate the cross sections and concentrations, the NIBC is applied by modifying the burnup of the gadolinium cells with the mean value of neighboring burnups. In our APOLLO3[®] calculation scheme, this is done by modifying the input cross section files that are produced by the lattice calculation step, for each assembly that contains gadolinium-loaded cells.
- in the core calculation, the depletion loop is modified to apply the NIBC after each depletion step. In the APOLLO3[®] calculation scheme, the pin-wise burnup values that are used to interpolate the cross sections are contained in a mesh field, that allows to easily locate cells and their neighbors and that can be modified with simple operations directly on the fields.
- after the interpolation of the macroscopic cross sections, the pin-wise burnup values are reset to their values before the NIBC, so that the burnup values in the gadolinium cells remain consistent, which is needed when using those values to compare to other calculations for instance.

In the 3D PRATIC core calculation, the added operations compared to a standard depletion loop (modifications of the pin-wise burnup values) cost less than a second per depletion step.

3.4. Obtaining Reference Results

The ideal candidate as reference calculation to evaluate the performances of the NIBC would be the lattice calculation of each configuration, since no spatial homogenization is done and advanced depletion resolution is used (predictor-corrector, parabolic flux extrapolation). However, this would only be feasible on the assembly, difficult on the 2D core because of the time and numerical resources it would require, and not feasible on the 3D core because the lattice calculation is exclusively carried on 2D geometries.

Since the challenge for gadolinium resides in the accurate prediction of a temporal parameter, a way to improve the prediction on the local burnup is to refine the depletion time steps. Indeed, the error committed on the prediction of the local burnup on step $i + 1$ is directly linked to the width of the interval, especially when a flat flux approximation is done as in core calculations with APOLLO3[®]. As an illustration, in the Figure 3, we compare the k -eff coming from a core calculation of a 2D assembly to the k -eff of the lattice calculation that provided the homogenized data. On one hand, the standard calculation uses the same global burnup steps as the lattice, while on the other hand the same steps have been refined to have intervals smaller than 2 MWd/t. The refined depletion steps yield much more accurate results with respect to the reference lattice calculation, with less than 10 pcm (10^{-5}) of difference, meaning that a core calculation carried on very small time steps can be considered a reference depletion calculation.

Figure 3. Impact of the time steps' fineness on the accuracy of the depletion (2D assembly)

4. RESULTS

Performances of the NIBC are evaluated on the three configurations proposed in 3.1. The quantities that are analyzed are the multiplication factor k -eff and the pin power distribution, in 2D and in 3D when applicable. In the following, as discussed in the previous section, performances are evaluated against reference core calculations that use very fine depletion steps (with intervals smaller than 2 MWd/t).

4.1. 2D Single Internal Assembly

In this section, the NIBC was applied on a single internal assembly, which is the one containing 36 gadolinium pins. Reflection boundary conditions were applied.

The Figure 4a shows the discrepancies on the k -eff with respect to the reference calculation for a deple-

tion performed with NIBC and one without, all the other parameters being equal. The behavior for the discrepancy without NIBC shows an underestimation of the reactivity of about 180 pcm at the gadolinium peak, before returning to more acceptable discrepancies once the gadolinium has disappeared. On the other hand, the calculation with NIBC leads to less than 40 pcm of error all along the depletion, although no clear improvement appears in the mean pin power error shown in 4b. On this 2D assembly calculation, the application of NIBC yields an accurate estimation of the reactivity during all the irradiation time without the need to refine the time steps.

(a) Error on the k -eff

(b) Mean values of the absolute errors on the pin power

Figure 4. Performance of the NIBC on the 36 gadolinium pins assembly

4.2. 2D PRATIC Core

In this section, we show the results of the application of the NIBC on the PRATIC 2D unrodded core. This enables to challenge the NIBC on heterogeneous situations, with gadolinium-loaded pins close to the radial reflector. As shown in Figure 5a, the application of the NIBC allows for a much better computation of the k -eff during depletion, with a maximum discrepancy of 100 pcm, while the standard calculation reaches a discrepancy of 320 pcm.

(a) Error on the k -eff

(b) Mean values of the absolute errors on the pin power

Figure 5. Performance of the NIBC on the 2D PRATIC core

To analyze further the performances, the Figure 6 shows the pin power discrepancy distribution at 7500 MWd/t, which is the peak of reactivity discrepancy. We can observe a center/periphery imbalance, that can reach -2.8% at the periphery and 3.8% in the center for the standard calculation. This imbalance is

largely reduced when applying the NIBC, with absolute maximum errors of about 1.5%. The Figure 5b confirms the better behavior of the pin powers thanks to the NIBC all along the depletion. The mean value of the absolute errors on the pin powers can reach up to 0.7% with the standard depletion, while the NIBC limits that mean error to 0.3%.

Figure 6. Pin power error distribution at 7500 MWd/t on the North-East quarter of the PRATIC 2D core (without NIBC on the left, with NIBC on the right)

The use of the NIBC leads to a better interpolation of the macroscopic cross sections of the Gadolinium isotopes in the gadolinium pins, and thus to more accurate absorption rates and to a better power distribution on the whole 2D core.

4.3. 3D PRATIC Core

The results of the application of the NIBC on the 3D core of the PRATIC benchmark are displayed in this section. On top of the radial leakage, we now challenge the depletion calculation with axial ones.

The NIBC is done as for the 2D core, considering each axial plane as independent from the others. This means that the neighbors considered in the calculation of the mean burnup are only the ones in the same plane as the Gadolinium cell. The discrepancies on the k -eff (Figure 7a) and on the pin power distribution (Figure 7b) for the 3D core are higher than for the 2D configuration for both simulations, with and without NIBC. For the standard depletion, the k -eff discrepancy reaches up to 800 pcm while the mean error on the pin powers reaches up to 1.5%. Again, the simulation with NIBC allows for a decrease of almost half of the error, at most 430 pcm on the k -eff and 0.8% on the pin power mean error.

(a) Error on the k -eff

(b) Mean values of the absolute errors on the pin powers

Figure 7. Performance of the NIBC on the 3D PRATIC core

The use of the NIBC on this 3D test case confirms that the choice of a more accurate interpolation parameter for the macroscopic cross sections of the Gadolinium isotopes impacts positively the whole calculation accuracy. Errors are diminished on the reactivity and on the power distribution at each time step of the whole depletion calculation, without any need for refined depletion time steps.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The depletion of fuel pins containing neutron absorber, such as Gadolinium, has proven to be a complex fit for traditional two-step deterministic calculations. Because the absorption cross sections of such isotopes are so high, inaccuracy in the estimation of their concentrations and of their cross sections can lead to very large errors on the whole core calculation, which are aggravated at each time step of the calculation because of positive feedback effects. This article explained the implementation in the APOLLO3[®] deterministic code of the NIBC method, as proposed in [1], and studied its effects on the depletion calculation of different configurations of the PRATIC benchmark, including the full 3D core.

The results displayed in this paper confirm that the choice of the interpolation parameter for the macroscopic cross sections of Gadolinium cells is essential for the accuracy of the depletion calculation. Replacing the use of the local burnup, which is very hard to assess in the gadolinium cells using homogenized nuclear data, with the mean value of the local burnups of the neighboring cells (i.e. "standard" fuel pins or guide tubes) leads to a drastic decrease of the error on both the reactivity and the power distribution, without any need for a refined time mesh, and thus with no additional expensive flux calculations.

The benchmarks chosen in this article to study the impact of the NIBC on depletion calculations are still quite simplistic. While it gradually builds up to a whole 3D small core calculation, the choice of carrying a nominal depletion (100% nominal power, no rods insertion) with no critical boron calculation and without any thermal-hydraulics feedback is not very representative of a real core calculation. Future works will focus on the elaboration and the analysis of a more realistic benchmark to highlight the contributions of the NIBC to a better calculation of a more realistic cycle, including thermal-hydraulics feedbacks and rod insertions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Jeon et al. "Neighbor-informed burnup correction for gadolinia depletion in pin-homogenized core calculation." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 192**, p. 109946 (2023). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454923002657>.
- [2] R. Vuiart et al. "PRATIC: A soluble-boron-free, pressurized water cooled, SMR core benchmark." *EPJ Nuclear Sci Technol*, **volume 10**, p. 25 (2024). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024026>.
- [3] P. Mosca et al. "APOLLO3[®]: Overview of the New Code Capabilities for Reactor Physics Analysis." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, pp. 1–14 (2024). URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00295639.2024.2334992>.
- [4] N. Gérard Castaing et al. "SIGAR: An APOLLO3[®]-based framework for PWR analysis." *International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science and Engineering (M&C 2025)* (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/xyz-47119>.